

Figure SM1. Mean values of (A) taxonomic richness (S), (B) Shannon-Wiener diversity ($H'\log_2$), (C) Pielou evenness (J'), (D) Hurlbert rarefaction (ES_{50}), (E) density (ind. m^{-2}) (N), and (F) biomass ($\text{g wet weight m}^{-2}$) of the macrofaunal communities along the transects A-H, arranged from south to north of Santos Basin, SW Atlantic considering data from 400-1900 m depth. Box limits = $\text{Mean} \pm \text{SE}$, Bars = $\text{Mean} \pm 2 \cdot \text{SD}$. One-way ANOVA: richness – $F: 1.560, p=0.155$; diversity – $F: 1.207, p=0.305$; evenness – $F: 0.638, p=0.724$; rarefaction – $F: 0.752, p=0.628$; density – $F: 1.835, p=0.088$; biomass – $F: 3.596, p=0.0002$. Lowercase letters above each bar indicate statistical significance according to Tukey pairwise test for unequal n ($\alpha = 0.05$).